

Integrating Sustainable Design in Southwest Nigerian University Buildings to Mitigate Climate Change Impacts on Staff and Students

¹ALAKA, C. D., ²ONYEGIRI, I., & ³ASIKOGU, L. I.

¹ Department of Architecture, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, Nigeria

^{2&3} Department of Architecture, Imo State University, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: chikodi.alaka@oouagoiwoye.edu.ng +2348068270254

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Abstract

The viability of life on earth is facing growing challenges as a result of climate change caused by human activities. As the effects of this climate change intensify, the university community faces increasing pressure to create resilient and sustainable environments for learning and work. However, universities worldwide are actively working to address climate change in order to reduce its impact on the university through sustainable design. Therefore, the integration of sustainable design principles in Nigerian university buildings becomes imperative. The study investigates the integration of sustainable design principles in university buildings across Southwest Nigeria, focusing on the current state of sustainable design, awareness level, barriers and mitigation strategies in these universities. A mixed-methods approach was employed in this study, combining physical building inspections, questionnaire administration, and interviews with key stakeholders, including architects, facility managers, and university administrators. Findings highlight critical deficiencies in current building practices and underscore the potential of sustainable design principles such as passive ventilation, solar energy systems, thermal insulation, and green landscape planning to improve indoor environmental quality and energy efficiency. The study concludes that adopting sustainable design in university architecture not only reduces environmental impact but also creates resilient, healthier learning environments, contributing to broader climate adaptation goals in the Southwest Nigerian universities.

Keywords: Buildings, Climate change, Passive design, Staff and students, Sustainable design

INTRODUCTION

The global urgency to address climate change has intensified the need for sustainable solutions across all sectors, especially within the university-built environment. Climate change poses a serious challenge, particularly in tropical regions such as Nigeria, which is characterized by rising temperatures, erratic rainfall patterns, worsening humidity, and high energy demands that affect not only infrastructure but also the health, productivity, and comfort of building occupants (Efeizomor, 2023). Universities, which serve as intellectual hubs for research and innovation, are particularly vulnerable, given their dense populations and diverse functional spaces. These institutions are expected to provide safe, conducive, and resilient environments for both staff and

students. Anber & Esmal (2018) emphasized that when students are uncomfortable or distracted by poor lighting, heating, cooling and ventilation, their ability to learn and concentrate suffers.

However, with the emergence of sustainable design (SD), which has gained significant attention in the building industry in recent years, provides a strategic response to climate change by reducing its environmental impact, conserving energy, enhancing indoor environmental quality, and improving overall resilience of buildings (Darko *et al.*, 2017). Sustainable building is one designed to be energy efficient, environmentally friendly, cost-effective, as well as to improve occupants' health and comfort (Tomasowa, 2018).

Globally, universities are at the forefront of integrating SD principles, not only in building construction and retrofitting, but also in curriculum development, research and policy-making (Aishuwaikhat & Abubakar, 2008). For example, institutions in Europe and North America have adopted green building standards such as LEED, BREEAM, and Passive House to reduce operational costs and environmental impact while improving occupant satisfaction (Fong *et al.*, 2014). Sustainable campuses also serve as living laboratories where innovative design and energy-efficient solutions are implemented and studied in real-world settings, inspiring broader societal change (Leal Filho *et al.*, 2018).

In Nigeria, the adoption of sustainable design in universities remains limited, as their universities often contend with aging infrastructure, poor thermal performance, inefficient energy systems and limited access to modern environmental control systems (Ayoko *et al.*, 2023). These inefficiencies not only increase operational costs but also exacerbate carbon emissions, undermining national and global sustainability goals. Therefore, in this study, understanding sustainable design and its connection with climate change mitigation is critical for developing practical strategies that bridge existing gaps. The study also assesses the level of thermal comfort experienced and discomforts experienced in the university buildings and the current state of SD in the Nigerian universities.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed-methods research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches. This design was selected to provide a comprehensive understanding of the state of sustainable design in public universities in Southwest, Nigeria, by integrating numerical data with in-depth qualitative insights. The mixed-methods approach aligns with Diffusion of Innovation Theory which explains how new ideas such as sustainable building practice can be implemented and adopted within a social system over time and Socio-technical Systems Theory, which emphasize the interaction between environmental design, human behavior, and institutional systems achieving sustainability outcomes. This theoretical alignment ensures both measurable physical indicators (quantitative) and contextual human factors (qualitative) are examined in relation to sustainable university environment. Purposive sampling method was employed for both the selection of universities, buildings and interviewers. Although purposive sampling limits statistical generalizability, it was suitable for this study because it enables the selection cases that are information-rich and contextually relevant for exploring sustainable design practices in Nigerian public universities. Three (3) universities, which include Olabisi Onabanjo University Ago-Iwoye (OOU), Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta (FUNAAB) and Osun State University, Osogbo (UNIOSUN), were selected based on geographic spread across Southwest Nigeria and the willingness of university management to grant access for data collection. The

selected universities reflect a cross-section of public institutions in Southwest Nigeria in terms of age, (old and new generation), Large and mid-size institutions, funding structure (federal and state), and academic focus. OOU, a state owned institution representing older-generation universities with large student's population. FUNAAB, a federal owned university while UNIOSUN, a new generation university with evolving infrastructure. This diversity allows for comparative insights into the sustainability of their built environments. Within the selected university, six (6) buildings each were purposively selected and inspected to assess the sustainable design features incorporated in them; this includes site zoning, energy efficiency systems, natural lighting, ventilation, material use and waste management systems. 125 questionnaires were administered to staff (academic and non – academic) and students of the selected universities to capture occupants' satisfaction, comfort levels and thermal discomfort experienced in university buildings, out of which 105 questionnaires distributed were returned. The questionnaire comprised both closed-ended and five-point Likert scale questions. The instrument was pilot-tested with 10 respondents in a non-sampled university to ensure clarity and reliability; a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.82 confirmed acceptable internal consistency. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were also conducted for twelve (12) interviewees (four from each university) to include architects, facility managers and university administrators to explore their knowledge of sustainable design and barriers to its implementation. The data collected were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. Descriptive statistics including frequencies and percentages were computed to summarize demographic data, satisfaction levels, and thermal comfort responses and represented using a simple pie chart. Interview transcripts and inspection notes were analyzed thematically. Emerging themes were grouped under key categories and interpreted using theories.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results integrate findings from physical building assessments, questionnaire surveys, and interviews to provide a comprehensive understanding of the state of sustainable design in public universities across Southwest Nigeria. The result shows that about 56% of students and 29% staff represent the distribution of the 84% questionnaires that were retrieved. While 61.40% of staff and students, as shown in Figure 1, reported an uncomfortable state of the buildings, particularly during the dry season, most of the respondents justified that by reporting feelings of excessive sweating/hotness during lectures or office hours, fatigue, leading to reduced concentration and productivity represented in Figure 2. This means that the principles of sustainable design were not fully integrated into the buildings, thus affecting the indoor environmental quality. This trend is also attributed to the fact that most classrooms and offices do not utilize ceiling fans or air conditioning, largely due to intermittent power supply and inadequate funding for energy-intensive systems.

Figure 1: Level of Thermal Comfort and Satisfaction Experienced

Figure 2: Types of Thermal Discomfort Experienced

Physical Assessment of Selected Buildings

A total of six (6) buildings, including lecture halls, administrative offices, studio, and hostel were assessed in each of the selected universities. Result shows that the buildings adhered to site zoning but lacked shading devices, had poor thermal comfort, with indoor temperatures exceeding 39°C at the time of visit. Passive design strategies were limited, increasing reliance on inefficient mechanical cooling, which were often inoperative due to intermittent power supply. Water conservation measures were minimal, with no rainwater harvesting system and limited low-flow fixtures. Solar photovoltaic cells were rare, with only one building equipped with small-capacity panels. Construction materials were mainly conventional, with only 29% locally sourced, contributing to a higher carbon footprint and limited recyclability. Waste management was in place but lacked recycling practices, and some waste disposal facilities were inadequate. Overall, the buildings demonstrated minimal sustainable design integration, highlighting the need for enhanced passive features, renewable energy, local materials, and waste recycling.

Analysis of Interviews

The interview featured twelve (12) professionals (architects, facility managers, and administrators), all of whom were selected by expert and purposive sampling methods. The interview questions were basically on sustainable design awareness, implementation and barriers. The interview responses are presented as follows:

i. Sustainable Design Awareness and Implementation: While 80% of professionals interviewed acknowledged understanding of sustainable design, less than 30% had practical experienced in integrating it into campus projects. This highlighted a significant gap between awareness and implementation of SD principles in universities. Thus, while awareness and interest are increasing, implementation is constrained by institutional fragmentation as in the case of OOU, inadequate funding mechanisms, and limited technical capacity. Overcoming these challenges requires not only technical solutions but also organizational change, policy reform, and capacity-building programs.

ii. Level of Integration: All the participants consented that their university has started integrating SD into their buildings, but at a slow pace, reflecting a cautious and incremental approach rather than a comprehensive transformation. While this demonstrates a positive shift towards environmental consciousness in the university development, the gradual progress may limit the immediate benefits of sustainable design in addressing pressing environmental challenges. This shows that there is institutional inertia and poor coordination between social and technical subsystems of the universities which is hindering innovation diffusion and the mainstreaming of sustainability principles in these institutions.

iii. SD Integration Barriers in Universities: The interviews highlighted shared significant barriers to effective SD integration in university buildings. All participants pointed to the absence of a clear institutional policy, limited budget allocations, and inadequate training in climate-responsive architecture as major barriers hindering the effective integration of SD in Nigerian universities. One architect in the physical planning unit emphasized that “budgetary provisions for maintenance are barely enough to keep lights on, not to fund new solar installations”. Collectively these barriers indicated that achieving sustainable design integration in Nigerian universities will require a multi-pronged approach to overcome systemic obstacles and accelerate the transition towards climate-resilient university infrastructure.

CLIMATE-RESPONSIVE SUSTAINABLE DESIGN STRATEGIES

Sustainable design strategies are essential in addressing the ongoing and imminent impacts of climate change. Based on the findings of this study and supported by insights from existing literature, this section lists the SD strategies proposed by the study that could be applied in university buildings to deal with the climate change impact. University buildings should be designed or retrofitted to optimize their orientation, incorporate appropriate shading devices and maximize natural ventilation. This approach can significantly improve airflow; reduce indoor temperature and energy consumption in the building. Evidence from Egwabor (2024) shows that optimizing building orientation, using shading devices, trees and enabling natural ventilation can reduce indoor temperatures by up to 5°C, thereby reducing cooling loads and improving comfort for students and staff. Given the abundant solar resources in Southwest Nigeria, universities should invest in decentralized renewable energy solutions, particularly for high-demand areas such as lecture halls, laboratories and administrative buildings. Improving the energy performance of buildings will enhance the thermal and visual comfort of the users. Photovoltaic (PV) systems can be deployed on rooftops and shaded walkways to provide reliable, off-grid energy while reducing

dependence on fossil fuels. Oladokun & Odesola (2020) demonstrated that small-to medium scale PV installations in universities could offset up to 40% of annual grid electricity consumption, improving energy security and reducing operational costs. To reduce indoor heat and improve thermal comfort, the installation of green roofs on buildings is recommended. This study aligns with Souza *et al.*, (2018), who found that green roofs can reduce the indoor room temperature by approximately 4.96 °C. Similarly, cool roofs constructed with reflective materials can further reduce heat absorption by up to 30% (Akbari *et al.*, 2009). Green landscaping should be prioritized in university planning as the presence of unshaded open spaces provides an opportunity for incorporating vegetation and green corridors to reduce heat island effects and improve microclimates. The findings of Mpundu & Shem (2024) indicated that campuses with richer vegetation reported lower levels of heat-related problems during the dry season.

Although rainfall is seasonal in Nigeria, rainwater harvesting systems (RWH) should be encouraged in campuses to reduce dependency on municipal supply and contribute to sustainable water management in universities. Studies have shown that RWH can improve hygiene conditions in hostels, toilets and cafeterias. Rahman *et al.*, (2014) demonstrated that properly sized RWH systems can meet up to 60% -70% of a building's annual portable water needs, thereby reducing the energy required to pump water through boreholes. For institutions with extensive roof surfaces, this approach could also contribute to storm water management, reducing flood risks during heavy rains. Also deploying smart controls such as occupancy sensors, automated shading, and programmable thermostats should be encouraged to help optimize energy use. In South African universities, Masekameni *et al.*, (2021) reported that intelligent lighting and HVAC controls reduced annual electricity use in lecture halls by up to 22%. These strategies can be adapted in Nigerian campuses to enhance operational efficiency. In addition, stakeholders should gear towards training programs and demonstration buildings that could showcase the benefits of Sustainable design. Such initiatives could serve as catalysts for institutional change and policy reform.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The promotion of sustainable design is to pursue a balance among economic, social, and environmental performance in implementing construction projects. This study has examined the integration of sustainable design within the university buildings in Southwest Nigeria as a means of mitigating the adverse impacts of climate change on staff and students. Findings reveal that most existing university buildings in the Southwest lack climate-responsive features, resulting in high levels of thermal discomfort, increased energy dependency, and reduced productivity among occupants.

Despite widespread awareness of the principles and benefits of SD, actual implementation remains limited in Nigerian universities due to institutional, financial, and regulatory barriers. The absence of design policies tailored to the local climatic factors has further contributed to the construction of buildings that are ill-suited for a warming environment. However, the study identifies significant strategies for low-cost, high-impact interventions such as passive ventilation, solar energy deployment, rainwater harvesting and green landscaping. These interventions, if strategically adopted, can enhance environmental performance, reduce operational costs, and improve the health and well-being of the university community. Therefore, integrating SD into their physical development not only supports Nigeria's climate adaptation but also demonstrates leadership in environmental stewardship and educational resilience. This study is not without limitations, as the

research focused only on three public universities in Southwest Nigeria. Findings may not be fully representative of universities in other geopolitical zones. Thus, further research involving larger samples and broader geographical coverage would strengthen the generalizability of the findings and inform more context-specific sustainable design strategies.

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